

Livelihood Enhancement of Agroforestry Farmers from Production of Banana and Plantain (*Musa species*) in Egbeda Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study examined the livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers from the production of *Musa species* in the Egbeda Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. A multistage sampling procedure was used for the selection of ninety-five (95) Agroforestry farmers from four (4) wards in the study area. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze data for the study. The results revealed that the majority of respondents were males (69.5%), about 30.5% of respondents fall within the age range of 40-50, 54.7% of the respondents were married being the majority. Also, the results showed that the majority of the respondents (44.2%) practiced crop farming with agroforestry as their livelihood activity. The result further showed that the majority of respondents (64.2%) sourced for suckers from their fellow farmers. Seasons do not affect production (71.6%), the majority of respondents (81.1%) plant suckers from fellow farmers as planting material. The results also revealed that the majority of the respondents (63.2%) have increased income from production, improved income from sales of banana and plantain (77.9%), and improved living standards (92.6%). Furthermore, the result revealed significant influence between agroforestry farmers' age ($\chi^2= 8.778$, $p= 0.032$) and livelihood activities ($\chi^2=13.304$, $p= 0.001$) on their livelihood enhancement, and also the result showed a significant relationship between production practices in banana production on their livelihood enhancement ($r= -0.026$, $p=0.037$). In conclusion, the study revealed that most agroforestry farmers' experienced livelihood improvement through banana and plantain production. It is therefore recommended that more improved banana and plantain cultivars should be introduced by subject matter specialists to agroforestry farmers to improve their income and to further give them a better life.

Keywords: *Musa species*, Production, Management Practices, Livelihood Improvements, Oyo State, etc.

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Introduction:

Banana and plantain (*Musa species*) occupy a strategic position for rapid food production in Nigeria (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2010). It is ranked third among starchy staples. The country's output doubled in the last 20 years. Production of *Musa species* is concentrated in the Southern part of Nigeria which remains largely in the hand of small-scale farmers who have ingeniously integrated it into various cropping systems. Production is male-dominated while women essentially handle marketing. The inadequate knowledge of improved cultural practices of crops by the farmers, an inefficient system of extension services, and skewness of specialization in areas of research are part of the reason why the yield potential of banana is still low in the country. Contributions of plantain to the income of rural households in major producing areas in Nigeria continue to increase tremendously in the last few years. *Musa species* are plants producing fruits that remain starchy at maturity need processing before consumption (Adeniji and Tenkouano, 2008). *Musa species* production in Africa is estimated at more than 50% of worldwide production (FAO, 2004).

West and Central Africa contribute 61% and 21% respectively (FAO, 2006). It is estimated that about 70 million people in West and Central Africa derive more than 25% of their carbohydrates from banana making it of the most important sources of food energy throughout the African lowland humid forest zone (Ayanwale, 2016). Nigeria is one of the largest bananas producing countries in the world (FAO, 2004). Forest soils are good for cocoa, oil palm, and rubber production and are also the main soil types in the plantain and banana producing regions of Nigeria.

Musa species production is mainly in the southern states of Nigeria which include Akwa-Ibom, Cross-River, Imo, Enugu, Rivers, Edo, Delta, Lagos, Ogun, Osun, and Oyo states (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2010). *Musa species* are produced in these states and transported to other parts of the country. The demand for banana and plantain within the country is very high with supply struggling to meet demand. This has created serious competition on the status of this crop as a foreign exchange earner. It remains an important staple food as well as the raw material for many products. It also serves as a source of revenue for many people and as raw material for industries producing value addition to other products in many parts of Nigeria. Banana occupies a strategic role in food production. It is a perennial crop with a short gestation period. It is a major source of carbohydrate for more than 50 million people.

In Nigeria, all stages of the fruit (from unripe to overripe fruit) is used as a source of food in one form or the other, the unripe are peeled and dried then made into flour, it can also be boiled or roasted as food or made into chips while overripe is used industrially as a composite in making of baby food ('Babena') biscuits and others products (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2010). Although the fruits are produced all year round, the major harvest comes in the dry season (November to February). Thus, it plays important role in bridging the hunger gap and also assists agroforestry farmers to earn more cash and to possess cash at hand during sales of banana (Tenkouano *et al.*, 2019).

Presently, unlike in the past few years, the processing of *Musa species* has turned into a big and small and medium business both in major cities and small towns in southern Nigeria. However, the major challenge limiting the availability of banana and plantain in the country is post-harvest losses among others. Bautista and Esguerra (2007) reposed that poor handling and sorting have resulted in postharvest disease and losses. Moreover, environmental factors such as temperature, relative humidity, and air composition contribute to the deterioration and destruction of the shelf-life of banana.

Udosen (2016) ascertained that inadequate storage systems, poor distribution, lack of ripening techniques coupled with environmental factors are responsible for a large proportion of

the product being wasted over time. Hence, this paper examined the contribution of banana and plantain (*Musa species*) production to livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers in Egbeda Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the paper include: examine the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents; identify sources of *Musa species*; identify *Musa species* available for production; examine management practices; and assess the contribution of *Musa species* production to livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers in the study area. The hypotheses of the study include no relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers; no relationship between banana production and livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers in the study area.

Materials and methods:

The study was carried out in Egbeda Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. The headquarters of Egbeda LGA is located at Ajoda town. The local government is occupying a landmass of 420.75 km². The geographical coordinates of Egbeda lies in 7°22'0" North and 43°0'0" East. The study area is basically rainforest vegetation with certain part being a derived savannah. It is bounded in the north, south, west and east by Irewole, Lagelu, Ibadan north, and Ona-ara government areas respectively (Tomori, 2012). The local government area comprises 11 wards which are Erunmu, Egbeda, Owobale, Olodo 1, Olodo 2, Monatan, Olode, Alugbo, Olubadan Estate, Kasumu and Ayede (Tomori, 2012).

The population of the area consists of commercial and smallholder farmers. Multistage sampling technique was employed for sample selection. Egbeda local government area was purposively selected in the first stage due to a large number of the population practicing agroforestry farming. Secondly, 30% of 11 wards in the local government were selected using a simple random selection. Therefore, the numbers of wards selected for the study were three (3) and these were Erunmu, Egbeda, and Ayede. The sample size was selected from these three wards with a random selection of 95 agroforestry farmers. A well-structured questionnaire was used for collection the data from the sample size of 95 agroforestry farmers.

The data collected were analyzed using frequencies, simple percentages, and chi-square and PPMC as inferential statistical tool to test for relationship between the variables of the hypotheses.

Figure 1: Map of Oyo State showing the study: Egbeda LGA

Results and discussion:

The result in Table 1 reveals that the majority of the respondents (69.5%) were males. This indicated male respondents engaged more in the propagation of *Musa species* among agroforestry farmers in the study area. This result corroborated with the findings of Ayanwale *et al.* (2018) that plantain production was mainly dominated by males who were monogamously married. The majority of the respondents (30.5%) that engaged in banana propagation were in the age range of 41 to 50 years. This indicated that the farmers involved in the production of banana were middle-aged men. The result aligned with the submission of Ayanwale *et al.* (2018) that the mean age of farmers that engaged in plantain production was 49 years \pm 13. The majority of the respondents (54.7%) were married. This is an indication that marriage infers commitment and responsibility which influence banana production in the study area. The result negated the findings of Faturoti *et al.* (2009) that singles were predominantly involved in the production of *Musa species*. The majority of the respondents (82.1%) had a household size of 1-5. This indicated that family size influences the robust production of banana as some household members assist in the farm area. Also, about 44.2% of the respondents engaged in crop farming as one of the other livelihood activities in the study. This indicated that crop farming was another livelihood activity of the agroforestry farmers which enhances banana species production. This result corroborated with Dimelu (2015) that most household farmers involved in mixed cropping were producers of plantain and banana in Nigeria. About 49.5% of the respondents had banana and plantain farms

ranging from 1 to 2 acres. This indicated the predominant and robust production of *Musa species*. This result aligned with the findings of Ayanwale *et al.* (2018) that many household farmers' farm size was less than 1 hectare. Also, about 37.8% of the respondents had an annual yield of 500 kg -1000 kg of banana. This indicated that banana production is a lucrative business in the study area. This result corroborated with the findings of Akinyemi *et al.* (2017) that an average yield of 345.20-1,024.29 kg of banana and plantain were harvested and traded by farmers. Furthermore, about 44.2% of the respondents had annual income ranging from ₦100,010–₦150,000. This is an indication that banana production among agroforestry farmers contributed to their annual income. This result aligned with the submission of Ayanwale *et al.* (2018) that the mean annual income from sales of *Musa species* was ₦97,000.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents in the study area (n = 95)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	66	69.5
Female	29	30.5
Age		
21-30	19	20.0
31-40	25	26.3
41-50	29	30.5
>50	22	23.2
Marital status		
Single	16	16.8
Married	52	54.7
Divorced	13	13.7
Widow (er)	14	14.8
Household size		
1-5	78	82.1
6-10	13	13.7
>10	4	4.2
Other livelihood activities		
Crop farming	42	44.2
Livestock farming	23	24.2
Marketing	30	31.6
Farm size (acres)		
1-2	47	49.5
3-4	44	46.3
>5	4	4.2
Yield per annum (kg)		
≤500	30	31.6
501-1000	36	37.8
1001-1500	22	23.2
>1500	7	7.4
Income per annum (₦,000)		
<100,000	30	31.6
100,010-150,000	42	44.2
151,000-200,000	18	18.9
>200,000	5	5.3

The result in Table 2 shows that the majority of the respondents (64.2%) were able to

source for the suckers of *Musa species* from their fellow farmers in the study area. This result indicated that most of the agroforestry farmers got their planting material from their fellow farmers very close to them in the study area. This result corroborated with the submission of Adeoye *et al.* (2013) that most farmers, about 92% sourced their planting suckers directly from their fellow farmers.

Table 2: Sources of *Musa species*

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Fellow farmers	61	64.2
Research institutes	27	28.4
Ministry of Agriculture	4	4.2
Private horticultural farms	3	3.2

The result in Table 3 revealed that the majority of the respondents (60%) stated that *Musa accuminata* was available and 67.4% of respondents also stated *Musa balbisiana* too was available in the study area. This result indicated that *Musa accuminata* and *Musa balbisiana* were predominantly available for production by agroforestry farmers in the study area. This result corroborated with the findings of Adewole (2017) that *Musa species* of different varieties were predominantly available in southwest Nigeria as one of the staple foods.

Table 3: *Musa species* Available for Production among agroforestry farmers²

Variables	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
<i>Musa accuminata</i> (Wild Banana)	57 (60.0)	38 (40.0)
<i>Musa balbisiana</i> (Plantain)	64 (67.4)	31 (32.6)
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> (Hybrid Banana)	28 (29.5)	67 (70.5)

The results in Table 4 revealed that the majority of respondents (71.6%) stated that seasons do not affect the production of banana and plantain in the study area. This indicated that the cultivation of *Musa species* thrives in both rainy and dry seasons due to its perennial nature. This result corroborated with the submission of Sense (2016) that *Musa species* need both hot and humid environments with an average temperature of 30°C and rainfall well distributed throughout the year.

Furthermore, the majority of the respondents (81.1%) propagated banana with suckers sourced from their fellow farmers. This indicated that the banana and plantain suckers were sourced from fellow farmers which eased the stress of looking for planting materials and enhanced the robust production of banana and plantain in the study area. The result aligned with the reposition of Agbongiarhuoyi *et al.* (2016) that the majority of farmers sourced their planting materials from the fellow farmers. The majority of the respondents (56.8%) applied inorganic fertilizer on their farms. This is an indication that the application of fertilizer was an important value addition to the robust production of banana. This result aligned with the submission of Norgrove and Hauser (2014) that the majority of smallholder farmers involved in the cultivation of plantain applied fertilizers as a cultural practice.

Also, the majority of the respondents (76.8%) stated that the length of maturity of banana

² Percentage in parentheses

ranges from 9 months to more months. This is indicated that the duration of banana and plantain production takes up to 9 months or more. This result conformed to the opinion of Agu (2018) that farmers need 8-9 months to harvest fully mature fruits of plantain and banana.

Table 4: Production Practices in Cultivation of *Musa species* by Agroforestry farmers³

Variables	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Seasons do not affect production of <i>Musa species</i>	68 (71.6)	27 (28.4)
Use of suckers from tissue culture for propagation	22 (23.2)	73 (76.8)
Use of suckers from fellow farmers for planting	77 (81.1)	18 (18.9)
Spacing of suckers during planting is essential	65 (68.4)	30 (31.6)
Application of inorganic fertilizer very important	54 (56.8)	41(43.2)
Use of agrochemicals important for production	17 (17.9)	78 (82.1)
Length of maturity between 9 months and 11 months	73 (76.8)	22 (23.2)
Some species matures in 12 months or more	28 (29.5)	67 (70.5)

The result in Table 5 showed that the majority of the respondents (63.2%) signified that there were more sources of income from the production of banana and plantain, and about 77.9% of the respondents established that there was an increase in their income from banana and plantain sales after harvest. Furthermore, the majority of the respondents (92.6%) had improved living standards. This indicated that banana and plantain production was a lucrative business among the agroforestry farmers which was evidential in its contribution to their livelihood enhancement in the study area. This result corroborated with the findings of Akinyemi *et al.* (2010) that the production of *Musa species* production has tremendously raised the income of rural livelihoods.

Table 5: Contribution of *Musa species* production to livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers⁴

Variable	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Increase in sources of income	60(63.2)	35(36.8)
Improvement of income after sales	74(77.9)	21(22.1)
Improvement in standard of living	88(92.6)	7(7.4)
Contribution to food security	49(51.6)	46(48.4)

The results in Table 6 revealed that age ($\chi^2=8.778$, $p<0.05$), and livelihood activities ($\chi^2=13.304$, $p<0.05$) of the respondents are significantly related to the contribution of *Musa species* production to livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers. This result implies that the age of farmers and their other livelihood activities have a high level of dependency on the contribution of *Musa species* production to the farmers' livelihood enhancement. This indicated that the farmers' age and other livelihood activities were germane factors of years of experience and practice in *Musa species* production that contributed to livelihood enhancement of the agroforestry farmers in the study area. This result corroborated with the findings of Kainga *et al.* (2014) that the average age of *Musa species* farmers was approximately 45 years and their other livelihoods

³ Percentage in parentheses

⁴ Percentage in parentheses

mean to contribute to livelihood improvement.

Table 6: Chi-square relationship between the respondents' socio-economic characteristics and contribution of *Musa species* production to livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers

Variables	χ^2	p-value	Decision
Sex	2.846	0.092	Not significant
Age	8.778	0.032	Significant
Marital status	6.487	0.090	Not significant
Household size	2.177	0.337	Not significant
Other livelihood activities	13.304	0.001	Significant

df = degree of freedom, χ^2 = Chi-square coefficient, p = probability level of significant, $p \leq 0.05$ (significant)

The result in Table 7 showed that there is a significant level of dependency between the production of banana species and livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers ($r = -0.026$, $p < 0.05$). This result implies that respondents' production of practices had a strong influence on livelihood enhancement of the farmers indicating production practices are favorable and impactful on livelihood enhancement of the agroforestry farmers in the study area. This result aligned with the submission of Sengar *et al.* (2019) that all the management practices involved in the production of *Musa species* raise the yield of banana and plantain thereby enhancing income and sustaining the livelihood of farmers.

Table 7: Pearson product moment coefficient showing relationship between production of banana species and livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision
Production and livelihood enhancement	-0.026	0.037	Significant

r = correlation coefficient, P = probability level of significance, $P \leq 0.05$ (significant), correlation coefficient (r) significant at 0.05 level of significance

Conclusion and recommendations:

This study examined the livelihood enhancement of agroforestry farmers from the production of *Musa species* in Egbeda Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings showed that the majority of the farmers engaged in banana production were males and middle-aged men. They were also married and practiced crop farming as an additional livelihood on some acres of land with banana and plantain production. This result showed that most of the agroforestry farmers got their planting material from their fellow farmers.

The findings also revealed that *Musa accuminata* and *Musa balbisiana* were predominantly available for production by agroforestry farmers in the study area. There were a varied number of management practices that helped in the production of *Musa species* which contributed to livelihood enhancement in the study area. The annual yield of 500kg-1000kg accrued to their production with an annual income of ₦100,010-₦150,000. Banana production

was a lucrative business in the study area with improved income and enhanced living standards. The recommendations are as follows; there should be the introduction of effective extension services to rural agroforestry farmers by subject matter specialists in order to meet their information needs of improved banana and plantain cultivars for cultivation. Also, adequate loans and credit should be made available to the farmers for farm expenditure, and purchases of inputs necessary for improved value-chain production.

References:

- Adeniji, T. A. and Tenkouano, A. (2008). Effect of processing on the proximate, mineral and pasting properties of whole flour from some new plantain and banana hybrid pulp and peel mixture. *Journal of Tropical Agriculture, Food, Environment and Extension*. Vol. 7 (2); pp. 99-105
- Adeoye, I. B., Oni, O. A., Yusuf, S. A. and Adenegan, K. O. (2013). Plantain Value Chain Mapping in Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*. Vol. 4 (16); pp. 137-146
- Akinyemi, S. O. S., Aiyelaagbe, I. O. O. and Akyeampong, E. (2010). Plantain (*Musa species*) Cultivation in Nigeria: A Review of Its Production, Marketing and Research in the Last Two Decades. *Acta Horti*; 879, pp. 211-218
- Akinyemi, S. O. S., Adejoro, M. A., Layade, A. A., and Adegbite, O. O. (2017). Market Structure and Performance for Plantain and Banana. *International Journal of Fruit Science*; Vol. 17 (4), pp. 440-450
- Ayanwale, A., Fatunbi, O. and Ojo, M. (2018). Baseline Analysis of Plantain (*Musa species*) Value Chain in Southwest of Nigeria. Vol. 3 (1). pp. 1-84
- Agbongiarhuoyi, A.E., Ayegboyin, K.O., Ogunlade, M.O., and Orisajo, S.B. (2016). Farmers' Use of Banana instead of Plantain as Shade Crop in Cocoa Establishment: A Case of Cross River State, Nigeria. *WorldRuralObservations*. Vol. 8 (1). pp. 14-22
- Agu, Z. (2018). Detailed Guide to How to Grow Plantains. Available at <https://legit.ng>1150513>
- Bautista, O.K. and Esguerra, E.B. (eds.) (2007). Post-harvest Technology for Southeast Asian Perishable Crops. Second Edition. University of the Philippines Los Banos and DA-Bureau of Agricultural Research. p. 447.
- Dimelu, M.U. (2015). Involvement of Farm Households in Banana and Plantain Production. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*; Vol.19 (1); pp. 105-116
- Faturoti, B.O., Ajayi, A.R., Baiyeri, P. and Madukwe, M.C. (2009). Impact of International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Banana (*Musa species*) Production Technologies on Smallholder Farmers in Southern Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences*; Vol. 9:2592-2598
- Food and Agriculture Organization (2006). *The State of Food and Agriculture in 2006*. Retrieved

September 22, 2019 from www.fao.org/dorcep/./ao800e

- Food and Agriculture Organization AGROSTAT Database. (2004). *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Production Yearbook. FAO, Rome.
- Kainga, P. E., Okorji, C. E., and Nweze, N. J. (2014). Socio-economic determinants and productivity of Banana and Plantain Production. *Global Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Health Sciences*. Vol. 3 (1); pp. 26-31.
- Norgrove, L. and Hauser, S. (2014). Improving Plantain (*Musa* spp. AAB) Yields on Smallholder Farms in West and Central Africa. *Journal of Food Sec.* Vol. 6: pp. 501-514
- Sengar, S., Manoj, K., and Caudhary, R. (2019). Banana Farming for Enhancing Income and Sustaining, Livelihoods. *Krishi Jagran*. Retrieved September 22, 2019 from <https://krishijagran.com/featured/banana-farming-for-enhancing-income-and-sustaining-livelihoods/>
- Sense Agric. (2016). Plantain (*Musa* spp.) Production Manual. Retrieved September 22, 2019 from www.agriculturenigeria.com
- Tenkouano, A., Lamien, N., Agogbua, J., Amah, D., Swennen, R., Traore, S., Thiemele, D., Aby, N., Kobenan, K., Gnonhour, G., Yao, N., Astin, G., Sawadogo-Kabore, S., Tarpaga, V., Issa, W., Lokossou, B., Adjanohoun, A., Amadji, G.L., and Adangnitode, S. (2019). Promising High-Yielding Tetraploid Plantain-Bred Hybrids in West Africa. *International Journal of Agronomy*. Retrieved September 22, 2019 from <https://www.hindawi.com>ija>
- Tomori, S. A. (2012). Memorandum on Local Government Administration 2nd Edition. Pp. 120-176
- Udosen, J. S. (2016). Economic Analysis of Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) Marketing in Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja, Nigeria. Online Master's Thesis. Retrieved September 22, 2019 from www.kubanni.abu.edu.ng